

Task 4.4A (Subtask 3): Implement External-Authority Validation for Metadata Values

Technical Report

Owner: Stanford University

Revision History

Date (YYYY-MM-DD)	Version Number	Revision Reviewed / Approved By	Brief Description of Change
Feb 12, 2025	v1	Document created by Attila L. Egyedi (egyedia@stanford.edu), from the Stanford University team.	
Feb 20, 2025	v2	Document updated by Mete U. Akdogan (mete@stanford.edu), from the Stanford University team.	Added the following sections: Introduction, Problem description, Solution, Integration into the user interface, and System impact
Feb 27, 2025	v3	Document reviewed by Marcos Martinez-Romero (marcosmr@stanford.edu), from the Stanford University team.	
Feb 28, 2025	v4	Document updated by Mete U. Akdogan (mete@stanford.edu) and Attila L. Egyedi (egyedia@stanford.edu), from the Stanford University team.	Addressing the comments from Marcos Martinez-Romero (marcosmr@stanford.edu)
Mar 12, 2025	v5	Revision approved by the Stanford team.	Addressed NIH feedback

Purpose

This technical report documents the implementation of external-authority validation for metadata values in the metadata management tools used by the RADx Data Hub, focusing on ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) validation for researcher identifiers and ROR (Research Organization Registry) validation for institutional affiliations. This work corresponds to subtask 3, *Implement External-Authority Validation for Metadata Values*, under task 4.4A, *Evaluate and Improve Metadata Quality and Reusability*.

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Introduction

Accurate, consistent, and reliable metadata are crucial for effective data management, search, and interoperability across systems. Metadata values enable users and applications to discover, filter, and manage resources efficiently. However, without proper validation, metadata can suffer from issues such as typographical errors, outdated references, or misapplied terminology. These inconsistencies ultimately degrade metadata quality and undermine the trustworthiness of associated datasets.

One approach to ensuring metadata consistency is to validate metadata values against authoritative external sources. An external authority source is a trusted repository that provides a standardized set of terms, identifiers, or code lists often maintained by recognized experts or institutions. By integrating external-authority validation, organizations can reference a trusted, canonical set of terms, identifiers, or code lists to verify that newly entered or updated metadata values meet established standards. This validation process helps reduce duplication, and eliminates arbitrary or incorrect entries.

The primary goal of implementing external-authority validation for metadata values is threefold:

1. **Improve Data Quality** - Ensuring that metadata entries adhere to recognized external standards increases consistency and reduces errors across datasets.
2. **Enhance Interoperability** - Standardized metadata facilitates seamless data sharing and retrieval across different departments, systems, and even organizations.
3. **Enrich Metadata** - By referencing external authorities, additional details (e.g., affiliations, organizational hierarchies, or research profiles) can be automatically retrieved, thereby adding depth and value to existing metadata records.

In the RADx Data Hub, which hosts structured and machine-actionable metadata for key entities like studies and data files, external authority sources play a critical role in maintaining the FAIRness of data. For instance, capturing the organization responsible for creating or maintaining a data artifact requires more than just a text label; instead, relying on a unique identifier ensures disambiguation, standardization, accuracy, and easier updates. By leveraging external authority sources, the Data Hub not only upholds metadata consistency but also strengthens the overall quality and interoperability of the metadata.

This report details the technical approach, methodologies, and tools involved in building and deploying an external-authority validation mechanism to the Metadata Viewer used in the RADx Data Hub.

Problem Description

Among the two prominent and widely recognized external registries for capturing research-related metadata fields that the RADx Data Hub metadata template accommodates are:

1. [Open Researcher and Contributor ID \(ORCID\) \[1\]](#) – Introduced in 2012 and maintained by the nonprofit organization ORCID, Inc., this system provides a persistent digital identifier that uniquely distinguishes researchers and authors. ORCID IDs are widely used by publishers, funders, and institutions to accurately track scholarly works and affiliations, helping to prevent name ambiguity, support reliable attribution, and enhance the overall integrity of research outputs.
2. [Research Organization Registry \(ROR\) \[2\]](#) – Established in 2019 by a coalition including Crossref [3], DataCite [4], and the California Digital Library [5], ROR is an open, community-led registry that assigns unique identifiers to research organizations and affiliations. By standardizing how institutions are identified, ROR helps improve data quality and interoperability across scholarly infrastructures. Its growing adoption by universities, publishers, and funding agencies underscores its importance in accurately managing and tracking institutional data.

ORCID and ROR both provide global, persistent identifiers. In the RADx Data Hub these registries can be referenced in the following metadata fields:

- **Data File Creators**
 - Creator Identifier
 - Creator Affiliation Identifier
- **Data File Contributors**
 - Contributor Identifier
- **Data File Distributions**
 - Distribution Publisher Identifier
- **Data File Funding Sources**
 - Funder Identifier

The screenshot shows a form with two input fields. The first field is labeled "Funder Identifier" and contains the text "ROR 0493hgw16". The second field is labeled "Funder Identifier Scheme" and contains the text "ROR - (https://ror.org)".

Figure 1: Fields for the funder identifier and scheme in the RADx Data Hub data file metadata - reflecting the current status.

However, in the current implementation, shown in Figure 1, users must first select the identifier scheme (i.e., “ORCID” or “ROR”) and then manually enter the corresponding identifier as a free-text string. This approach poses several issues:

1. **Lack of Validation:** No mechanism verifies whether the entered string is a valid ORCID or ROR. As a result, it is easy to enter a malformed or incorrect identifier, leading to inaccurate metadata.
2. **Error-Prone Process:** Reliance on manual text input increases the likelihood of typos and other data entry errors.
3. **Context Dependence:** The text field for the identifier depends on the separate “Scheme” field to signal whether the string should be interpreted as an ORCID or a ROR. This contextual link can be overlooked or misunderstood, further exacerbating the risk of invalid data.

Without validation or standard formatting guidance, the metadata records become inconsistent and unreliable, potentially hindering discoverability and interoperability of research data.

Solution

To address the shortcomings of relying on plain-text input for ORCID and ROR identifiers, we introduced two new field types into the CEDAR template model [6], where [CEDAR](#) [7] serves as the metadata management system for the RADx Data Hub. Specifically, these new types are:

1. Externally validated ORCID identifier (**ext-orcid**)
2. Externally validated ROR identifier (**ext-ror**)

By defining these specialized field types, we ensure that external registry identifiers are clearly and explicitly recognized as ORCID or ROR values rather than arbitrary text. Furthermore, these fields are integrated with the [ORCID API](#) [8] and [ROR API](#) [9], allowing the system to automatically verify that each entered identifier exists and is correctly formatted.

At the instance level, the system stores both the **Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI)** and a corresponding **rdfs:label**, which captures additional descriptive information (e.g., the researcher's name in the case of ORCID or the institution's name for ROR). Figure 2 illustrates examples for each field type.

This approach not only ensures that entered identifiers are accurate but also enriches the metadata with valuable contextual information.

```
{
  "ORCID-Field": {
    "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3325-793X",
    "rdfs:label": "Mark Musen"
  },
  "ROR-Field": {
    "@id": "https://ror.org/00f54p054",
    "rdfs:label": "Stanford University"
  }
}
```

Figure 2: An illustration of how data are stored at the instance level for ORCID and ROR fields.

Once an identifier has been validated, users can also retrieve extra details from these external authorities. For instance:

- **ORCID** - biography, verified email domains, employment information, keywords, and country
- **ROR** - organization type, links, location, and relationships

Implementation Details

In order to make this new functionality available to the end-user, changes were made in two tiers of the system:

- Frontend - responsible for the presentation of the User Interface, and for the User eXperience
- Backend - responsible for the communication with the external authorities and providing data to the frontend

Backend Services Integration - ROR

ROR offers a [public API](#) which can be used without any kind of authentication. The public API offers the option to retrieve detailed information about a research organization. It also allows users to search for organizations based on name fragments.

CEDAR's newly implemented backend services leverage these calls, offering a unified API towards our end-users (and our frontend).

Backend Services Integration - ORCID

ORCID offers a [public API](#) which can be used with user credentials, available after a registration process available to the general public.

This API is slightly different than the ROR, it requires steps to retrieve a token, which then can be used as authentication data for the individual API calls. Tokens expire, and they need to be renewed.

CEDAR's backend uses ORCID's authentication system, but hides it behind CEDAR's code, so our end-users (and our front-end) are presented with a unified API symmetrical in functionality with the ROR API. Also, CEDAR's API does not require authentication from the end-user, thus making it easy to integrate with ORCID taking advantage of CEDAR's API.

Frontend Integration

To accommodate the new **ext-orcid** and **ext-ror** field types, we enhanced three CEDAR tools: (1) the Template Designer, used to create new metadata templates, (2) the Metadata Editor, used to create or modify metadata, and (3) the Metadata Viewer, a RADx Data Hub component that provides a user-friendly visualization of metadata.

In the following, we describe the improvements made to the Metadata Editor and the Metadata Viewer, as these tools have the most direct impact on the RADx Data Hub community. The Metadata Editor is available to submitters to generate standardized metadata, while the Metadata Viewer allows visitors of the RADx Data Hub website to visualize metadata for data files. The enhancements impacting the Metadata Editor are illustrated in Figures 3–6, while the changes affecting the RADx Data Hub Metadata Viewer are illustrated in Figures 7–9.

Real-Time Search and Validation

ORCID Field

When a user begins typing a researcher's name into the ORCID field, a dropdown list automatically appears with matching results from the ORCID API. The user must select one of these entries; otherwise, the input is cleared to ensure that only a valid, existing ORCID record is used, shown in Figure 3. Alternatively, if the user knows the researcher's ORCID, it can be entered directly. In this case, if the entered ORCID is valid, only that researcher's record will be present in the list, Figure 4.

The screenshot shows a browser window titled "Example ORCID Field". The search input field contains the text "Peter". Below the input field, a dropdown menu is open, displaying five search results. Each result consists of a name followed by an ORCID iD and a link to the ORCID profile page. The results are: ABBA PETER - https://orcid.org/0009-0005-2969-5226, AJI PETER - https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8343-5605, ALAN BASIL PETER - https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5474-2275, AMRUTHA PETER - https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2100-0347, and ANGELA PETER - https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4496-2511.

Figure 3: An example name search in an ORCID field - User types "Peter" into the ORCID field, the dropdown displays researchers whose first or last names include "Peter" along with their corresponding ORCIDs.

The screenshot shows a browser window titled "Example ORCID Field". The search input field contains the ORCID iD "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9981-9750". Below the input field, a dropdown menu is open, displaying a single search result: Peter W Rose - https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9981-9750.

Figure 4: An example ORCID search - User types in an ORCID of the researcher and the corresponding researchers is listed with name and ORCID.

ROR Field

The same mechanism applied in the case of the ORCID field applies to organization identifiers. Users can type the name of an institution, triggering a query to the ROR

API. The dropdown then displays potential matches, guaranteeing a valid organizational ID, illustrated in Figure 5. Alternatively, if the user knows the institution's ROR, it can be entered directly. If the entered ROR is valid, only that institution's record will appear in the list, shown in Figure 6.

The screenshot shows a search interface titled "ROR Example ROR Field". The search input contains "San Diego". Below the input is a dropdown list of results:

- San Diego Spine Institute - <https://ror.org/0425kp210>
- San Diego Youth Services - <https://ror.org/03r1vfk75>
- Zoological Society of San Diego - <https://ror.org/04q1yyt92>
- University of California, San Diego - <https://ror.org/0168r3w48>
- California College San Diego - <https://ror.org/00vvhe852>

Figure 5: An example name search in an ROR field - User types "San Diego" into the ROR field, the dropdown displays institutions whose names include "San Diego" along with their corresponding ROR IDs.

The screenshot shows the same search interface as Figure 5, but the search input now contains the ROR ID "https://ror.org/0168r3w48". The dropdown list shows only one result:

- University of California, San Diego - <https://ror.org/0168r3w48>

Figure 6: An example ROR search - User enters an institution's ROR into the field, the matching institution is displayed along with its name and ROR.

Abstraction from Technical Details

Under the hood, the system seamlessly handles name-based searches, ID lookups, and URI validations. Users are not required to manually enter or confirm these details, thus significantly reducing data entry errors.

Access to Detailed Information

Once a user selects a valid ORCID or ROR entry, an additional "details" icon becomes available, illustration for ORCID field in Figure 7 and ROR in Figure 8. Clicking this icon reveals more information about the chosen researcher or

institution (e.g., a researcher’s biography or an organization’s location and type etc.), which is shown in Figure 9 for ORCID and Figure 10 for ROR.

Figure 7: ORCID field details icon - Once a valid ORCID entry is selected, an additional “details” icon appears, offering further information.

Figure 8: ROR field details icon - When a valid ROR entry is chosen, a “details” icon becomes available to provide extra details.

Peter Rose

Keywords: Structural Bioinformatics, Structural Biology, Structure Based Drug Design, Biomedical Informatics, Machine Learning, Scientific Software Engineering, Computational Chemistry, Knowledge Graphs

Country: US

Employment:

- Role:** Director, Structural Bioinformatics Laboratory
- Dates:** 2017-01-01
- Organization:** University of California San Diego
- Location:** La Jolla, California, US

- Role:** Site Head, RCSB Protein Data Bank West
- Dates:** 2007-10-01 to 2016-12-01
- Organization:** University of California San Diego
- Location:** La Jolla, California, US

Figure 9: ORCID field details - Clicking the “details” icon next to a valid ORCID entry displays extended information about the researcher, such as their employment and additional context.

 Example ROR Field

 <https://ror.org/0168r3w48>

University of California, San Diego

Organization Type	Links
Education, Funder	website
Relationships	wikipedia
Child Organizations	Location
California Sea Grant	San Diego, United States (California)
California Space Grant Consortium	
San Diego Supercomputer Center	
Scripps Institution of Oceanography	
UCSD-CNRS Joint Research Chemistry Laboratory	
Center for Wireless Communications	
Parent Organizations	
University of California System	
Related Organizations	
Rady Children's Hospital-San Diego	
Salk Institute for Biological Studies	
Scripps Mercy Hospital	
University of California San Diego Medical Center	
VA San Diego Healthcare System	
Open Data Commons for Spinal Cord Injury	
Moorea Coral Reef Long Term Ecological Research	
Materials Science in Extreme Environments	
University Research Alliance	

Figure 10: ROR field details - Selecting the “details” icon for a valid ROR entry reveals further information about the institution, including its location, type, and other relevant details.

By tightly integrating ORCID and ROR lookups into the metadata viewer, the RADx Data Hub ensures a more accurate, user-friendly experience. Users benefit from immediate validation of their entries, while metadata quality is preserved through standardized and verified references to external authorities.

Impact on the Metadata Generation and Visualization Workflow

Introducing dedicated ORCID and ROR field types enhances how identifiers are managed and validated. By seamlessly integrating these registries into the metadata management workflow, the system now offers a more robust, user-friendly, and accurate process for entering and verifying external identifiers. The improvements can be summarized in four key areas:

1. **Contextual Clarity**

Each field type is intrinsically tied to its respective registry, eliminating confusion about identifier formats and removing the need for separate “Scheme” fields. This direct mapping ensures that users are always aware of which registry they are referencing. As a result, the RADx Data Hub Metadata Viewer now presents external authority information more clearly, enhancing the overall readability and usability of metadata.

2. **Automated Validation via External APIs**

Integration with ORCID and ROR APIs validates identifiers in real time, minimizing typos or invalid entries. This automation reduces manual overhead and ensures that only correct, resolvable identifiers are captured in the metadata.

3. **Streamlined User Experience**

The user interface now allows for straightforward identifier entry without requiring a separate step to select a scheme. The system takes care of verifying inputs in the background, providing immediate feedback to guide users toward valid entries.

4. **Opportunities for Metadata Enrichment**

Because each identifier is confirmed against a trusted external source, additional details—such as researcher profiles or organizational structures—can be retrieved automatically. This enrichment creates more comprehensive and informative dataset descriptions.

These advancements not only improve data consistency but also foster greater trust in the metadata, as each record now reflects validated, authoritative information about researchers and their affiliations.

Limitations and Ongoing Work

As discussed, the primary tools affected by these improvements in the context of the RADx Data Hub community are the Metadata Editor and the Metadata Viewer. While these enhancements clearly improve metadata validation and visualization, the full impact on metadata creation—whether through new submissions or edits—will become clearer if the RADx Data Hub continues to receive contributions. This work lays the foundation for future metadata submissions by establishing a more structured and validated metadata infrastructure. These improvements will streamline metadata contribution workflows, ensuring that new metadata entries maintain high standards of accuracy and interoperability.

For the Metadata Viewer, the impact of these enhancements is clear, providing users with more precise and intuitive representations of external authority information. However, fully realizing these benefits requires an update to CEDAR's data file metadata template to incorporate the newly validated ORCID and ROR fields. This template update is currently in progress and, once completed, will further enhance metadata consistency and usability across the RADx Data Hub.

Moving forward, we anticipate expanding these validation mechanisms to support additional external authority fields. These efforts will further improve metadata reliability, searchability, and usability, strengthening the RADx Data Hub's role as a high-quality, standards-compliant metadata repository.

Resources

The code changes introduced by this task span across several GitHub repositories, including:

- Java Library:
 - <https://github.com/metadatacenter/cedar-artifact-library>
- TypeScript Library:

- <https://github.com/metadatacenter/cedar-model-typescript-library>
- Frontend integration:
 - <https://github.com/metadatacenter/cedar-template-editor>
 - <https://github.com/metadatacenter/cedar-embeddable-editor>
- Backend integration:
 - <https://github.com/metadatacenter/cedar-bridge-server>

References

[1] ORCID. Available at: <https://orcid.org>

[2] ROR. Available at: <https://ror.org>

[3] Crossref. Available at: <https://www.crossref.org>

[4] DataCite. Available at: <https://www.datacite.org>

[5] California Digital Library. Available at: <https://www.cdlib.org>

[6] CEDAR Template Model. Available at:
<https://metadatacenter.readthedocs.io/en/latest/developer-guide/template-element-and-fields/>

[7] CEDAR. Available at: <https://metadatacenter.org>

[8] ORCID API. Available at: <https://info.orcid.org/what-is-orcid/services/public-api/>

[9] ROR API. Available at: <https://ror.readme.io/docs/rest-api>